

English Language Learning Anxiety and Self-Efficacy of Learners in Modular Learning

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Abstract:

This study investigated the levels of English Language Learning Anxiety (ELLA) and self-efficacy among Grade 8 students engaged in modular learning. ELLA, often triggered by the fear of being corrected in front of peers, is a persistent challenge among language learners in face-to-face settings. The study sought to extend existing knowledge by examining ELLA in the context of modular learning and exploring its relationship with students' self-efficacy. Employing a descriptive-correlational research design, the study involved 262 Grade 8 students from a national high school in Western Visayas, Central Philippines during the School Year 2021–2022. Findings revealed that students experienced a moderate level of ELLA and a low level of self-efficacy. A significant negative correlation between ELLA and self-efficacy was also observed, indicating that anxiety remains prevalent even in home-based learning and adversely affects students' confidence in their English learning abilities. These results underscore the need for strategic guidance programs aimed at reducing language anxiety and enhancing learners' self-efficacy.

Keywords: English Language Learning Anxiety, Self-efficacy, Modular Learning Modality, Philippines

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

English as a second language is considered a crucial component of Philippines educational system (Jugo, 2020). The proliferation of its usage is so extensive that even children at a young age are already capable of speaking the language. Filipinos' excellent reputation in English language proficiency has driven investors in the Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) industries to invest in the country, which helped boost the country's economy (Bodwell et al., 2016).

However, recent reports from national achievement tests, proficiency examinations, and board examinations have affirmed that the country's English language proficiency is declining (Racca & Lasaten, 2016). In 2018, Senator Grace Po, alarmed by these results, filed a resolution to investigate the "decline" in English proficiency of Filipino students. Numerous studies focused their investigation on the main factors that affect the English Proficiency of non-native English speakers. As an emotional problem, evidence reveals that anxiety could highly affect learners' academic performance in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) (Sadiq, 2017). Affective factors affect language learning (Hidayati, 2018) because their emotions and feeling during the learning process interfere with their decisions and motivation. Jugo (2020) pointed out that speaking activities in a classroom are the primary source of foreign language learning anxiety. The fear of making mistakes, being corrected, and being negatively evaluated or criticized in front of the whole class is a significant source of anxiety for Filipino learners.

To add to this unfortunate scenario came the COVID 19 global pandemic, which shocked the whole world ((Miani et al., 2020) and became most detrimental to the education sector (Masuhay, 2020). All schools around the globe

went to an unexpected shutdown (Al-Samarrai, Gangwar, and Gala, 2020). As a Learning Continuity Plan, through DepEd Order no. 12, series of 2020, the Department of Education opted for Self-Learning Modules (SLMs). Self-learning modules must be answered by each student at home, without the guidance of a teacher; hence, self-efficacy, which is the belief in one's capacity to execute behaviors necessary to produce specific performance attainments (Bandura, 1977), is very important.

Previous studies and classroom observations by English teachers have witnessed the English language anxiety among students during face-to-face classes. Thus, it would be interesting to know their English language anxiety and self-efficacy if they are learning alone through self-learning modules, away from their usual learning setup in the classroom. These scenarios motivated the conduct of this study.

Current State of Knowledge

Numerous studies have explored the relationship between foreign language learning and anxiety, particularly in various learning environments. For instance, Ajmal (2019) reported that anxiety significantly affects the academic achievement and performance of distance learners in Allama Iqbal Open University. Similarly, other researchers have found a positive relationship between reduced language learning anxiety and the use of multimedia environments (P. Huang & Y. Hwang, 2013) as well as e-learning platforms (S. Aydin, 2018), consistent with the findings of Majid et al. (2012) on online language learning anxiety among adult learners.

Building on this, Hurd (2009) conducted a longitudinal study to investigate language anxiety in a distance learning context, revealing that after four months, 21% of students reported increased anxiety, 27% experienced a decrease, while 51.7% acknowledged that the educational setting impacted their performance. Likewise, Bollinger (2017), using the Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS), found that students in traditional face-to-face classes experienced lower anxiety levels than those in distance learning settings.

Ajmal and Ahmad (2019) further supported these findings by emphasizing that limited interaction with instructors in distance learning contributes to heightened anxiety, particularly among male students, negatively influencing academic outcomes. Hurd (2007) also identified specific sources of anxiety in distance education, such as the absence of immediate feedback, limited speaking practice, and diminished learner confidence. Nielson and Gonzalez-Lloret (2016) noted that weak community support and delayed interaction hinder language acquisition, which thrives on timely feedback and active engagement. Russell (2020) added that the abrupt transition to online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic, without students' choice in learning modality, further exacerbated these anxieties.

This growing body of literature underscores the importance of academic self-efficacy—a student's belief in their capability to learn, perform, and succeed academically (Bandura, 1977, 1986, 1997; Pajares & Miller, 1994). Self-efficacy can vary depending on task difficulty (Torres & Turner, 2016) and has been consistently linked to improved academic performance, motivation, and learning outcomes (Alyami et al., 2017; Doménech-Betoret et al., 2017). Koseoglu (2015) found that students who believe intelligence is malleable tend to exhibit higher levels of self-efficacy and academic confidence.

In the specific context of modular learning, Kock (2004) argued that the non-traditional nature of communication in distance language learning increases cognitive effort, heightens communication ambiguity, and reduces physical arousal or excitement—factors that can negatively impact the affective domain, including self-efficacy. As modular learning requires a high degree of motivation and self-management, only students with strong self-efficacy are likely to cope effectively (Wang & Zhan, 2020).

Further reinforcing this, Lisnychenko et al. (2020) found that changes in the learning environment, such as reduced personal interaction, Zoom fatigue, and increased deadlines, contributed to rising anxiety levels among students. These factors led to a negative attitude toward English classes, decreased motivation, and general avoidance behavior. Some students even reported not wanting to attend English classes ($t = 2.63$) and feeling more anxious in English classes than in others ($t = 2.26$). Such responses highlight how lowered motivation and increased anxiety in distance learning environments can adversely affect students' self-efficacy.

Theoretical Underpinnings

Theories advocating for the specific nature of a foreign language anxiety were started by the works of Horwitz, Horwitz and Cope (1986) and followed up later by MacIntyre (1999). According to Horwitz et al., Foreign Language Anxiety (FLA) is "a particular complex construct of perceptions of self, beliefs, feelings, and behavior, all of them related to classroom learning of a language, which arises from the unusualness of the whole process of language learning." Likewise, MacIntyre (1999) spoke of language anxiety as "the feeling of stress, nervousness, and worry associated with learning a second or foreign language." The two researchers underline that such negative emotional responses stem from obstacles to learning a new language and culture, especially in classrooms. Classroom speaking activities were identified by Jugo (2020) as a major source of classroom language learning anxiety. This research, however, investigates English language learning anxiety in the context of printed modular distance learning, where students study alone at home. Understanding that anxiety does influence language learners from this mode makes it necessary to understand how it does in order to provide relevant support.

Other than this, the concept of self-efficacy, which is a principal part of Bandura's (1997) social cognitive theory, evokes the mental estimation of the individual's capability for organizing and executing with energy the courses of actions required to attain designated ends/ Bandura also perceived a correlation between foreign language anxiety and self-efficacy: learners with low self-efficacy are more likely to experience high anxiety given their tendency to underassess their ability to learn a foreign language. In a self-regulated learning environment like modular learning, self-efficacy assumes a very important role. Gomes (2014) calls attention to the fact that students need to have high belief in their abilities to cope with self-directed task demands. If not, learners may find it hard to complete their modules leading to poor academic achievement.

Thus, this study aimed to evaluate the levels of English language learning anxiety and self-efficacy that are present among students involved in printed modular distance learning in the local context of the researchers. Because of the problems associated with modular learning, such as interpreting instructions on one's own without teacher support or managing tasks independently, the students should have heavily depended on their self-efficacy. Lack of confidence in their ability would lead to an increase in their anxiety, resulting in procrastination or total avoidance of the task. By studying the relationship between these two variables, this research hopes to generate insights or possible recommendations aimed at providing a supportive environment for learners in modular learning conditions.

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to determine the levels of English language learning anxiety (ELLA) and self-efficacy among Grade 8 learners under the modular learning modality in a national high school in Western Visayas, Philippines during the School Year 2021–2022. Specifically, it examined the learners' profiles based on sex, section, and average monthly family income. The study assessed the levels of ELLA and self-efficacy and investigated whether significant differences existed in these variables when grouped according to the identified demographic factors. Finally, it explored the relationship between ELLA and self-efficacy levels among the respondents.

Research Methodology:

This section presents the research design, data gathering procedure, other instrumentations, and statistical tools. It also discusses the parameters, especially the statistical tools, the respondents, and the study's locality.

Research Design

The declining English proficiency of Filipinos has been linked to language anxiety in classroom settings. With the shift to modular learning, learners must have high self-efficacy and low foreign language anxiety to successfully complete their English tasks. This study aims to measure the levels of English language learning anxiety and self-efficacy among learners in the researcher's locality using survey questionnaires. Employing a descriptive-correlational design, the study both describes the characteristics of the respondents (Akhtar, 2016) and examines the relationship between anxiety and self-efficacy (Fraenkel, Wallen, & Hyun, 2010), making it suitable for the study's objectives.

Study Respondents

The study population consisted of 821 Grade 8 learners enrolled in the modular learning modality during the School Year 2020–2021. From this total population, a representative sample was determined using Cochran's formula, which calculates an ideal sample size based on desired precision, confidence level, and estimated population proportion, making it especially suitable for large and heterogeneous populations (Al-Hemyari, 2018). The computed ideal sample size was 262 learners. To select the respondents, the simple random sampling technique was employed, ensuring that every member of the population had an equal chance of being chosen, thus maintaining the sample's representativeness and reducing bias (Bhardwaj, 2019).

Instrument

To investigate students' self-efficacy and English language learning anxiety in modular learning, two instruments were used. A 20-item researcher-made questionnaire, validated by experts and tested for reliability, measured English Language Learning Anxiety. For self-efficacy, the standardized 10-item Generalized Self-Efficacy Scale by Schwarzer and Jerusalem (1995) was employed. This widely used psychometric tool assesses positive self-beliefs in overcoming challenges, focusing on personal agency. Respondents rate items on a 4-point scale, with higher total scores indicating greater self-efficacy.

Data Gathering and Procedure

The study followed several key steps: the researcher first obtained permission from the Division Office and school principal, then secured parental consent for student participation. Questionnaires were distributed as hard copies alongside weekly modules for students to complete at home, with clear instructions provided. After collecting the responses, the researcher reviewed and validated them, then coded the data by assigning numerical values for

analysis. The data were classified, tabulated, and analyzed using SPSS, and conclusions were drawn based on the study's objectives.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objectives 1, 2, and 3 employed a descriptive analytical scheme, using the frequency count and percentage as a statistical tool to assess the profile of respondents, and mean to assess the levels of ELLA and self-efficacy. Objectives 4 and 5 utilized a comparative analytical scheme, applying the Mann-Whitney U test to determine significant differences in the level of ELLA and self-efficacy when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. Lastly, Objective 6 used relational analytical scheme, adopting Spearman rho to ascertain significant relationship between ELLA and self-efficacy of learners.

Ethical Consideration

By guaranteeing the confidentiality of the respondents' answers and upholding their anonymity during the whole research process, the study made a concerted effort to reduce the possibility of harm to its target respondents in accordance with Republic Act 10173, also known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012. Informed consent from parents and assent from the learners were also secured to ensure ethical participation in the study.

Results and Discussion:

This section presents, analyzes, and interprets the data gathered to carry out the pre-determined objectives of this study.

Profile of Respondents

Table 1

Profile of the Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Sex	Male	130	49.6
	Female	132	50.4
Section	Section A - H	124	47.3
	Section I - Q	138	52.7
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower (Below Php 7500)	129	49.2
	Higher (Php7500 and above)	133	50.8
	Total	262	100.0

It can be gleaned in the table that there is an almost even percentage among male (49.6%) and female (50.4%) respondents which suggests the grade 8 regular sections are not dominated by a particular sex because there is an almost the same number of male and female students. In terms of section, there are 124 students belonging to sections A-H while sections I-Q have 138 students. These data show that there is an almost even distribution of students among the regular sections.

Similar results can be seen in the average family incomes of the respondents, which shows that 129 grade 8 students have a lower average family monthly income and 133 higher average family income. The number of students with higher average family monthly income is 4 counts higher than those with lower family income but that is not a significant number which may imply that the school is catering an almost the same number of students with lower and higher average family monthly income.

Level of English Language Learning Anxiety of Learners in the Modular Learning Modality

Table 2

Level of English language learning anxiety of Grade 8 learners in the modular learning modality

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. I feel anxious when I am answering the tasks and activities of my English modules.	2.90	Moderate level
2. I feel intimidated when I see English modules with activities and tasks to answer.	2.78	Moderate level
3. I am nervous when I am reading a passage in my English modules.	2.53	Moderate level

4. I am more anxious to learn English at home through a module, than in school with a teacher.	2.74	Moderate level
5. I feel uncomfortable learning English by my own.	2.84	Moderate level
6. I cannot express my ideas well in English.	2.81	Moderate level
7. I do not want to take my English subject through modules because I do not think I can do it by myself.	2.64	Moderate level
8. I feel nervous that I have to learn English without my teacher.	2.71	Moderate level
9. I do not think I am doing well in my English subject as well as other modular learners do.	2.76	Moderate level
10. I am afraid to submit my answers when I know my teacher will check it.	2.74	Moderate level
11. I cannot finish working on my English modules because I easily get worried if I am doing well.	2.71	Moderate level
12. My heart is pounding every time I am answering the tasks and activities in my English modules.	2.71	Moderate level
13. I am not confident that I will learn a lot about English language through modular learning modality.	2.85	Moderate level
14. I am not satisfied with my modular learning strategies in the English subject.	2.84	Moderate level
15. I am afraid I may not improve my English language skills in this modular learning modality.	2.95	Moderate level
16. I worry about getting failing grades in my English subject.	3.05	Moderate level
17. It frightens me that I may not get the right understanding of the lessons in my English module.	3.05	Moderate level
18. I am nervous of the negative remarks that my teacher may give on my submitted tasks in my English modules.	3.1	Moderate level
19. I feel very self-conscious about my answers in my English modules.	3.1	Moderate level
20. I think I need more support and guidance in learning the English language in this modular learning modality.	3.03	Moderate level
Overall mean	2.84	Moderate level

The data in the table show that the level of English language learning anxiety of Grade 8 learners in the modular learning modality has an overall mean of 2.84 which is verbally described as "moderate level". It is safe to say that the grade 8 learners are indeed experiencing English language anxiety to some degrees while they are taking modular learning.

Items 16 and 17 which states "I worry about getting failing grades in my English subject.," and "It frightens me that I may not get the right understanding of the lessons in my English module," got the highest means of 3.05. It implies that students are most anxious about getting low grades and failing the subject. Most students do not want to repeat a grade level the next year, hence, they always strive to pass a subject by getting high grades. It affirms the idea of Russell (2020), who concluded that distance learners' anxiety worsened in our present situation due to COVID-19.

Meanwhile, item number 3 which states "I am nervous when I am reading a passage in my English modules," got the lowest mean of 2.53. It implies that they have lesser anxiety in reading English passages, but they are more anxious in not getting the right understanding of the English lesson. This result supports the findings in the study of Ajmal and Ahmad (2019) who found out that students feel more anxiety in distance learning approach, because, due to distance, they are unable to discuss or share problems with instructors on daily basis.

However, this result is contrary to the findings of Aydin (2018) who found out that students became less anxious in distance learning modality. There are noticeably few and contradicting results in the studies concerning language learning anxiety in modular learning modality.

Level of Self-Efficacy of Learners in the Modular Learning Modality

Table 3

Level of Self - efficacy of Grade 8 learners in the modular learning modality

Variable	Mean	Interpretation
Self-efficacy	23.49	Low Level

Table 3 shows that the grade 8 regular section students have a low level of self-efficacy as shown in their overall mean score of 23.49. This implies that students don't have a strong self-motivation and self-assurance to carry on learning tasks in the modular learning modality. It may also imply that they are not ready for this sudden change in learning modality as they are used to a classroom set-up where there is always a teacher to remind, motivate, and check on them for immediate feedbacking.

These findings are similar to that of W. Wang and J. Zhan (2020) who concluded that only those learners of good level of motivation and self-management skills can experience no or little causal effect of distance education, which may mean to say that most learners will feel the negative effect of the sudden change of learning modality to distance education, which is low self-efficacy, unless they have high level of motivation. A Lisnychenko, et. al. (2020) also claimed that a general tendency of anxiety to grow due to the changes in learning context, consequently, these changes reflect the growth of students' negative attitude to English classes, decrease of motivation and general avoidance.

Comparative Analyses

Table 4

Difference in the Level of English language learning anxiety of Grade 8 learners in the modular learning modality When Grouped and Compared According to Variables

Variables	Categories	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U - test	Sig. Level	p-value	Interpretation
Sex	Male	130	135.22	8096.00	0.430	0.430	Not Significant
	Female	132	127.83				
Section	Lower	124	123.42	7553.50	0.05	0.102	Not Significant
	Higher	138	138.76				
Average family monthly income	Lower	129	149.71	6230.00	0.000	0.000	Significant
	Higher	133	113.84				

Table 4 shows that there is no significant difference in the language learning anxiety of students in the modular learning modality when they are grouped according to sex ($p\text{-value } 0.430 > 0.05$). This result will accept the hypothesis "There is no significant difference in the level of English language learning anxiety of Grade 8 learners in the modular learning modality when grouped and compared according to sex." It implies that language learning anxiety does not differ according to sex. This result affirms the findings in the study conducted by Aflez (2019) who found out that both male and female students experience moderate language learning anxiety in online or distance learning.

However, this result is in contrast to that of Ajmad and Ahmal (2019), in their study "Exploration of Anxiety Factors among Students of Distance Learning: A Case Study of Allama Iqbal Open University", who found a significant difference between male and female university students regarding anxiety.

When grouped and compared according to section, the value $p = 0.102 > 0.05$ indicates that there is no significant difference in the language anxiety of the students in modular learning modality. Hence, the hypothesis "There is no significant difference in the level of English language learning anxiety of Grade 8 learners in the modular learning modality when grouped and compared according to section," is accepted. This means that language learning anxiety is of same levels across groups and sections of students in modular learning modality. This supports Ajmal M. & Ahmad S. (2019), who concluded that most of the students felt anxiety during distance learning because of different issues. Every student, no matter what group he is placed, since, the learning modality is at home, will feel the same anxiety and pressure as everybody else.

Moreover, when grouped according to family income, results show a $p\text{-value}$ of $0.000 < 0.05$, hence, there is a significant difference in the language learning anxiety of students from lower family monthly income ($M=149.7$) and higher family monthly income ($M=113.8$). Therefore, we have to reject the hypothesis "There is no significant difference in the level of English language learning anxiety of Grade 8 learners in the modular learning modality when grouped and compared according to family income." This means that students language learning anxiety in modular learning vary significantly according to average monthly family income, whereas students from lower group experience more anxiety that those students with higher family income. It may imply that students from the lower family income experience more challenges and difficulties while studying through modular modality which may be caused by a lack of support financially and emotionally by their parents whose focus are in looking for food and other basic needs. Meanwhile, respondents from a higher family monthly income may get more support financially, morally, emotionally from parents whose job may be more stable and can provide comfort to their children, hence, they may experience less anxiety.

These findings somehow agree to Malindog-Uy (2020) who argued that if Department of Education will continue distance education, the marginalized will be at a disadvantage. Students whose family are struggling financially might not be able to provide the needed support such as learning materials or technological gadgets that may aid students' learning to lessen their anxiety and stress. Hence, students from a family with lower average family income may experience more anxiety.

Furthermore, this study show similar results to the study of (Z.Zia & M Safi, 2020) who asserted that learners with lower socioeconomic background experienced higher levels of language learning anxiety compared to students with higher economic status.

Table 5

Difference in the Level of Self - efficacy of Grade 8 learners in the modular learning modality and When Grouped and Compared According to Variables

Self - efficacy							
Variables	Categories	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U - test	Sig. Level	p-value	Interpretation
Sex	Male	130	123.83	7598.00	0.104	0.104	Not Significant
	Female	132	139.05				
Section	Lower	124	141.10	7357.50	0.05	0.052	Not Significant
	Higher	138	122.87				
Average family monthly income	Lower	129	129.39	83.17.00	0.657	0.657	Not Significant
	Higher	133	133.55				

The table shows that when students are grouped and compared according to sex, there is no significant difference ($p = 0.104 > 0.05$) in the self-efficacy of both male and female students. Hence, the null hypothesis "There is no significant difference in the level of self-efficacy of Grade 8 learners in the modular learning modality when grouped and compared according to sex," will be accepted. This result supports the findings in the studies of Barış (2015), Rhema, & Miliszewska (2014), Yıldız (2016), and Yavuzalp, & Bahçivan, (2020), who found out that self-efficacy doesn't vary according to sex.

However, there are also studies showing that male students' attitudes towards online learning are more positive than female students (Fidan, 2016; Kaban, 2021; Yenilmez et al., 2017). It has been recorded in some studies that males' susceptibility to technology contributed to their positive attitude towards e-learning or distance learning (Fidan, 2016).

Moreover, when the students are grouped according to section, results show a $p\text{-value } 0.052 > 0.5$, which means that there is no significant difference in the self-efficacy of students in sections A-H and sections I-Q. Thus, the hypothesis, "There is no significant difference in the level of self-efficacy of Grade 8 learners in the modular learning modality when grouped and compared according to section," is accepted. It implies that self-efficacy does not differ according to section. This result partially opposes that of Ozaydin Ozkara, B., & Ibili, E. (2021), who found out that when students are grouped according to departments or majors, some groups recorded a higher self-efficacy than other groups.

Furthermore, the table shows that there is no significant difference ($p = 0.669 > 0.05$) in the self-efficacy of students from lower family monthly income and higher family monthly income. Hence, the hypothesis "There is no significant difference in the level of self-efficacy of Grade 8 learners in the modular learning modality when grouped and compared according to average family monthly income," is accepted. It means that students' self-efficacy doesn't var according to family income. Students from both groups feel the same low level of self-efficacy despite the notion that students with a more stable family income will feel more self-efficacy due to the financial and moral support that they might be more getting.

In oppose to the findings of the present study, however, is a study conducted by Zhou & Zhang (2021). They found out that family annual income had a significant impact on a student's perception of the learning community. It is interesting that the students from low-income families perceived more belongingness to the learning community compared to students rich families. This might be because students from low-income families have more freedom to do their own thing like contacting their friends in-person. On the other hand, students from high income families were more strictly prohibited to have face-to-face contact with their friends during COVID19.

Although the in-person interaction during COVID-19 is not safe healthwise, it might have helped them to have better socialization with their learning community in comparison to those high-income students who were constrained at home.

Relational Analysis

Table 6

Relationship between the level of English language learning anxiety and the level of self-efficacy of Grade 8 learners in the modular learning modality

Variables	rho	Significance Level	p-value	Interpretation
Level of English Language Learning Anxiety	-0.309	0.01	0.000	Significant
Level of Self-efficacy				

The table shows that there is a significant relationship ($p=0.000<0.01$) between students' language learning anxiety and self-efficacy while they are taking modular learning modality. The *rho value* -0.307 shows a negative relationship between the two variables. The results imply that as students' level of English language learning anxiety increases, their self-efficacy decreases. This leads us to reject the null hypothesis that states that "There is no significant relationship between the level of English language learning anxiety and level of self-efficacy of Grade 8 learners in the modular learning modality." Hence, we can safely conclude that students' anxiety towards English language learning affects their self-efficacy. The more they are feeling anxious, the more unconvinced they will become that they can carry out the tasks. Further, reducing language anxiety through supportive and engaging learning strategies may be essential in improving learners' confidence and performance in modular learning environments. This result affirms the result of the study by Barkanyi, Z. (2021) which found out a strong negative correlation between self-efficacy beliefs and foreign language anxiety.

Conclusion:

The Grade 8 regular education program using printed modular learning shows a balanced participation between male and female students, indicating equal interest from both sexes, and a fair distribution across heterogeneous sections. Interestingly, more students from higher-income families are enrolled despite the public school setting, suggesting strong parental trust in the school's quality of education. Findings reveal that students experience a moderate level of English Language Learning Anxiety (ELLA), indicating that anxiety persists even in self-paced, home-based learning. Across all sex, section, and income groups, students reported a consistently low level of self-efficacy, suggesting a lack of confidence in completing modular tasks, possibly due to limited guidance and motivation. While ELLA does not significantly differ by sex or section, it does vary significantly by family income, suggesting that financial factors influence language learning anxiety. Conversely, self-efficacy does not significantly vary across any of the demographic variables. Ultimately, the study found a significant negative relationship between ELLA and self-efficacy, confirming that as students' anxiety increases, their confidence to complete tasks decreases—highlighting the critical need for targeted interventions to reduce anxiety and enhance student belief in their academic capabilities.

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